

A deep learning approach to photospheric parameters of CARMENES target stars

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Abstract

In the light of more and more new instrumentation to get a deeper insight into the universe, tons of data are collected. While traditional machine-learning methods have been used in processing stellar spectral data, such large new datasets are better handled with Deep Learning (DL) techniques. In this work, we present a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) approach to derive fundamental stellar parameters (effective temperature, surface gravity, metallicity and rotational velocity) from high-resolution high signal-to-noise ratio spectra. We construct an individual CNN architecture for each of the four parameters and train them on synthetic PHOENIX-ACES spectra. After that, we apply the trained networks to the observed spectra of 50 M dwarfs observed with CARMENES. The CARMENES spectrograph, installed on the 3.5 m telescope at the Calar Alto Observatory (Spain) has two channels, covering the visible (0.52 to 0.96 μm , $R = 96,400$) and near-infrared (0.96 to 1.71 μm , $R = 80,600$) spectral ranges. We compare our results to literature values, and demonstrate that our method can be used for stellar parameter determination without the need of having a huge sample of stellar spectra with known parameters, because our networks can be trained on synthetic spectra. Introducing Deep Transfer Learning (DTL) in our approach allows us to transfer external knowledge about the stellar parameters (e.g., from interferometry) to our training set and therefore improve our results compared to literature.

1 Introduction

A detailed description of our approach together with an extensive literature summary on different stellar parameter determination methods is presented in Passegger et al. (2020). We will give a brief summary of our method in the following.

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are a family of machine

learning (ML) methods that are designed to learn from data using a structure similar to the human brain (Zhang et al., 1998; Anthony & Bartlett, 2009; Gong & Ordieres-Meré, 2016). An ANN is composed of a collection of artificial neurons or nodes that are arranged in different layers. Each node is activated by a nonlinear activation function (e.g., linear, rectified linear unit (ReLU), sigmoid, or softmax) and is charac-

terized as a linear function of its input signals with weights.

Deep learning (DL) is a subcategory of ML methods, where computational models consist of multiple layers to learn representations of data with multiple levels of abstraction (LeCun et al., 2015; Schmidhuber, 2015; Zheng et al., 2018). The main difference between DL and ML techniques is that in ML relevant features need to be identified by the user, whereas DL is able to learn and identify those features by itself.

ML has been used in many fields in astrophysics in the recent years, including extragalactic (Dieleman et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2018; Abraham et al., 2018), asteroseismology (Hu et al., 2017), variable stars (Mahabal et al., 2017), and stellar parameter determination (Ness et al., 2015; Fabbro et al., 2018; Sarro et al., 2018; Whitten et al., 2019; Birky et al., 2020; Antoniadis-Karnavas et al., 2020). In Passegger et al. (2020) we investigated the effects of different DL architectures, wavelength windows, and stellar parameter combinations on the model creation and training precision of a convolutional neural network. We also analyzed the uncertainties that were induced when the DL model was trained on synthetic spectra and then applied to observed spectra for parameter determination. The DL algorithm was implemented using TensorFlow v2 (Abadi, 2015) together with the front-end framework Keras (Chollet, 2015).

2 Method

2.1 Neural network structure

Figure 1 shows a basic representation of the deep neural network we employed in this work. It was constructed with several layers. The input layer is an one-dimensional synthetic spectrum, which is followed by a block of several convolutional layers. The convolutional layers create sets of features from the input spectrum. They can be imagined as filters that scan across the previous layer and convolve a certain sub-region of their input with weights in order to extract relevant features from the previous layer and pass it on to the next layer.

A pooling layer can be included between or after the convolutional layers depending on the architecture. In the pooling layer the spatial size of the feature representation is reduced to decrease the number of free parameters in the network. Concretely, their function can be seen as a window sliding across the last convolutional layer, calculating, e.g., the average or the maximum value of each sub-section.

Following the pooling layer is an ANN block constructed of neuron nodes organized in several fully connected layers, where every node of the previous layer is connected to every node of the following layer. The first layer is represented by the feature vector created from the previous convolutional layers. This is followed by several hidden layers. In general, the more hidden layers, the “deeper” is the ANN. The last layer is the output layer, containing the predicted stellar parameter.

2.2 Training

For the training a large number of spectra with known stellar parameters is needed as a reference set. In our case these spectra were synthetic spectra based on the PHOENIX-ACES stellar atmosphere models (Husser et al., 2013, see Section 3.1). The reference set was split into a training (95%) and a validation set (5%). The purpose of the training was to adjust all DL model parameters (i.e., the number and length of filters in each convolutional layer, filter coefficients, pooling

window size, number and weights of connection nodes in the fully connected layers) in order to minimize the error between input and estimated output stellar parameters. Therefore the whole training set was sent through the DL model (described as forward propagation, see Figure 1). After that the output stellar parameter was compared to the known input parameter, giving the training error. Through backward propagation the error can be used to modify the DL model parameters. Following this procedure, the validation set was fed into the DL model and the validation error (mean square error, MSE) was determined. This error provides an independent estimation of how the performance of the DL model was improved during the training. It is generally also used to avoid over-fitting, which happens when the DL model learns random variations in the training set (e.g., coming from tiny molecular features that the DL model considers as noise), instead of the relevant relations between the features and is therefore unable to generalize to new unseen data. Hence, the validation error should be continuously decreasing over time. Once its minimum was reached, all DL coefficients and weights were fixed and the model was applied to a test set.

In our case the test set consisted of 100 randomly generated synthetic spectra, that were never seen before by the DL model. The test error served as a quality estimation of the model prediction. We defined an error threshold for good quality models by adopting the MSE criterion, ranging between $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and 10^{-5} . If a model produced a difference between real and estimated parameters of less than the threshold, then the training phase is considered complete and the model is being applied to observed spectra for parameter prediction.

3 Analysis

3.1 Synthetic spectra grid

For training we utilized synthetic spectra. With this approach we had the advantage that we could generate an arbitrary number of synthetic spectra instead of being limited to a small sample of observations with well defined stellar parameters. We used the PHOENIX-ACES model grid presented by Husser et al. (2013) to generate our training sample. The grid was especially designed to model the atmospheres of cool dwarfs down to $T_{\text{eff}} = 2300$ K, incorporating a new equation of state to account for molecule formation. More information about the PHOENIX atmosphere code can be found in Hauschildt (1992, 1993); Hauschildt & Baron (1999).

We linearly interpolated the existing grid to increase the number of training samples and get a finer step size for the parameter values. The parameter range of the new grid covered $2300 \text{ K} \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 4500 \text{ K}$, step size 25 K, $4.2 \text{ dex} \leq \log g \leq 5.5 \text{ dex}$, step size 0.1 dex, and $-1.0 \text{ dex} \leq [M/H] \leq +0.8 \text{ dex}$, step size 0.1 dex. We also accounted for rotational velocities between 1.5 and 60.0 km s^{-1} by broadening the synthetic spectra with a Fortran translation of the `rotational_convolution` function of Eniric (Figueira et al., 2016).

In order to break the known degeneracies between T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[M/H]$ (Passegger et al., 2018, 2019), we used the PARSEC v1.2S evolutionary models (Bressan et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2014, 2015; Tang et al., 2014) to constrain the PHOENIX-ACES grid. Thereby, we removed synthetic spectra with physically unrealistic stellar parameter combinations (i.e., parameters that do not correspond to main-sequence M dwarfs) from the training grid. In total we ended up with

Figure 1: Illustration of neural network and training process. A wavelength range is fed into the network, and the stellar parameter is derived (forward propagation). The result is compared to the known input parameter and the error is calculated. The weights of the layers are adjusted through backward propagation. This is done until the error converges.

449 806 synthetic spectra for training the DL models. The synthetic spectra were adjusted to the observations by applying instrumental broadening by convolution with a Voigt profile. The parameters for the Gauss and Lorentz part were taken from Nagel et al. (2021, submitted). For continuum normalization of the synthetic and observed spectra we incorporated the Gaussian Inflection Spline Interpolation Continuum

(GISIC) routine¹ developed by D. D. Whitten.

3.2 Observational sample

We applied our DL method to the same template spectra as used in Passegger et al. (2019) and selected the first 50 stars of their sample listed in their Table B.1. The spectra were ob-

¹<https://pypi.org/project/GISIC/>

served with the CARMENES² instrument, which is mounted on the Zeiss 3.5 m telescope at the Calar Alto Observatory, Spain. CARMENES consists of two highly stable fiber-fed spectrographs covering a spectral range from 520 to 960 nm in the visible (VIS, $R \approx 94\,600$) and from 960 to 1710 nm in the near-infrared (NIR, $R \approx 80\,500$), as described in Quirrenbach et al. (2018); Reiners et al. (2018). The primary goal of CARMENES is to search for Earth-sized planets in the habitable zones of M dwarfs.

The CARMENES radial velocity pipeline *serval* (SpEctrum Radial Velocity AnaLyser; Zechmeister et al., 2018) produces high-S/N template spectra for each star with at least five individual spectra, which are used to derive the radial velocities of a single spectrum by least-square fitting against the template. We used these template spectra in our approach to derive stellar parameters.

The observations were corrected for the spatial motion of the stars by using the cross-correlation (*crosscorrRV* from PyAstronomy, Czesla et al., 2019) between a PHOENIX synthetic spectrum and the observed spectrum. In order to get a universal wavelength grid for applying the DL models, we linearly interpolated the wavelength grid of the observations to the original wavelength grid of the synthetic spectra.

3.3 Different DL approaches

During our analysis we trained DL models for different DL architectures (varying number of convolutional, pooling, and ANN hidden layers), different individual spectral ranges in the VIS and NIR as well as different combinations of them (ranges described in Passegger et al., 2019), and for individual stellar parameters and combinations of them. When we applied the different DL models to the PHOENIX-ACES test set we found that the differences in estimated stellar parameters were negligible. We also found that there were only minimal differences between the parameters derived from different spectral ranges, hence we concluded that, theoretically, there is enough spectral information in any range of any size. Therefore, we chose to use the range between 8800–8835 Å, because this range showed the smallest MSE from all ranges we investigated. Additionally, we decided to train individual models for each stellar parameter separately, because this setting yielded slightly smaller test errors than models that derived combined stellar parameters. By using the above mentioned quality criteria (see Section 2.2) we ended up with more than 200 accepted DL models for each stellar parameter.

3.4 Synthetic gap

The synthetic gap refers to the differences in feature distributions between synthetic and observed data (Fabbro et al., 2018). Although synthetic spectra have significantly improved over the recent years, they still can't fit observations perfectly.

We can visualize the synthetic gap by projecting the high-dimensional data (up to 4096 flux values, i.e. dimensions) onto a low-dimensional (e.g. 2-D) space. This procedure is called dimensional reduction and we utilized the Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP; McInnes et al., 2018) to preserve the local topology and show the

similarities between the PHOENIX and CARMENES spectra families. It can be seen in Figure 2 that only four out of 50 CARMENES spectra lie close to the PHOENIX family. The rest of the observed spectra is located far away from the PHOENIX spectra, which depicts significant differences in feature distribution between observed and synthetic spectra. These differences transform into higher uncertainties on the stellar parameters determined from these synthetic spectra. This applies not only to DL models trained on synthetic spectra while stellar parameter determination is done from observed spectra, but also to any other parameter determination technique that involves synthetic spectra.

Figure 2 also presents noisy PHOENIX spectra with a S/N of 150, which was considered to be the lower limit for the CARMENES spectra. The noisy spectra were produced by adding white Gaussian noise. With this we can investigate how noise could contribute to the synthetic gap, however we found that the noisy PHOENIX spectra are not closer to the CARMENES spectra than the noise-free spectra. This shows that noise cannot be responsible for the synthetic gap and is not relevant in this study.

Figure 2: UMAP two-dimensional projection of CARMENES (blue) and PHOENIX spectra ($S/N = \infty$ in yellow, $S/N = 150$ in gray) representing the flux values from the 8800–8835 Å. Only four CARMENES spectra are similar to the PHOENIX feature distribution, the rest show significant differences. Figure taken from Passegger et al. (2020), Fig. 4

4 Results

All DL models that passed the above mentioned quality criteria are applied to the 50 CARMENES spectra and the four stellar parameters T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[M/H]$, and $v \sin i$ were derived. The estimations from all DL models were collected to draw probability density functions using the Kernel Density Esti-

²Calar Alto high-Resolution search for M dwarfs with Exo-earths with Near-infrared and optical Échelle Spectrographs, <http://carmenes.caha.es>

Figure 3: DL estimations distribution for $[M/H]$ for the CARMENES star GJ 169.1A (J04311+589). The dark blue curve presents the Gaussian kernel density estimate. Our adopted estimation (i.e., the KDE maximum) is indicated by the red line. The 1σ uncertainties are shown as magenta lines as well as the result from Passegger et al. (2019) for this star with the green line. Figure taken from Passegger et al. (2020), Fig. 5.

mate (KDE; Rosenblatt, 1956; Parzen, 1962). The maximum of this function was considered as final estimation for each of the parameters of each star. The 1σ thresholds of the predictions were defined as uncertainties for each star and parameter. An example is shown in Figure 3.

4.1 Literature comparison

In Figure 4 we present a comparison of our results for T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[M/H]$ to literature values. We encourage the reader to refer to Passegger et al. (2020) for a plot regarding $v \sin i$ and a detailed discussion on each literature study we compared our results with. In the plots we differentiated between different determination methods in order to visualize possible biases. Regarding T_{eff} , our results are mostly consistent with literature within their errors, although there is a slight offset at the cool end as well as a larger spread for hotter stars. Interestingly, for the three stars we have in common with Antoniadis-Karnavas et al. (2020) we estimated a T_{eff} about 150 K higher than ODUSSEAS.

For $\log g$ we calculated literature values from masses and radii the respective studies provide, except for the spectral analysis from Passegger et al. (2019), who derived $\log g$ themselves. Although the latter values agree with our results very well, there is a slight offset for the spectroscopic literature values, showing higher values than ours.

In metallicity we distinguished between $[Fe/H]$ and $[M/H]$ derived by the literature studies. We compare both sets here, since $[Fe/H]$ are often used as a proxy for $[M/H]$. As can be seen from Figure 4 there is no clear correlation between our

results and literature. If we ignore data points from Passegger et al. (2019), we see that our metallicities are tentatively too high compared to literature.

4.2 Deep Transfer Learning

Transfer learning provides a robust and practical solution to leverage information from one domain to improve the accuracy of a model built on a different domain (Vilalta, 2018). In our case, transfer learning would look to overcome the difficulty of the synthetic gap. We selected 14 CARMENES stars with T_{eff} obtained from interferometry (Boyajian et al., 2008, 2012; von Braun et al., 2014) and tried to “transfer” that knowledge to the rest of the CARMENES stars. To do so, we chose the best DL model for T_{eff} in the range 8800–8835 Å and trained a set of ANNs using a different number of cross-validation folders (3, 4, and 5). This is a common way when dealing with a small reference sample and for dividing the group of 14 spectra with interferometric T_{eff} into training and validation sets. For example, using 5 folders we trained with 11 stars and used the other 3 for validation. Then, we train the ANNs using the convolutional features obtained with the selected DL model and apply the model to the other 283 observed CARMENES spectra.

CARMENES T_{eff} predictions for the best model obtained can be seen in Figure 5 in comparison with literature values. Comparing T_{eff} derived with DTL to the values from DL (black) it can be seen that DTL predicts slightly lower T_{eff} on average. There is also a turn-off visible at $T_{\text{eff}} < 3400$ K. A reason for this might be the lack of interferometric measurements at low temperatures, which makes it hard to transfer predictions to the remaining CARMENES data set in that range. Considering $T_{\text{eff}} \geq 3400$ K, DTL shows a smaller mean difference to literature values (49 K) than DL (61 K), meaning that some improvement was made.

As a next step, we will also try this DTL approach with the other stellar parameters, especially metallicity, using the estimations from FGK+M binaries as of Montes et al. (2018).

5 Summary

We present a deep learning neural network technique to estimate the stellar parameters T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[M/H]$, and $v \sin i$ for 50 M dwarfs from high-S/N, high-resolution, optical, and near-infrared spectroscopy. We trained the DL models with PHOENIX-ACES synthetic spectra, which gave us the advantage of generating a sufficient number of spectra with well known stellar parameters. During our analysis we investigated the effect of different architectures and spectral windows. The different settings showed only marginal effects on the derived stellar parameters. All DL models were able to successfully predict individual stellar parameters from synthetic spectra with high precision and accuracy. From this we concluded that there is enough spectral information even in a small wavelength range and that the performance of our DL algorithm is independent of the specific neural network architecture. Due to the synthetic gap, this only refers to the synthetic PHOENIX spectra and does not translate to the observed CARMENES spectra. We applied our DL models that passed the quality criteria to 50 high-resolution and high-S/N CARMENES spectra. Compared to other literature studies, our results for T_{eff} and $\log g$ mostly agree quite well, however there are significant deviations in metallicity. We conclude that these deviations can be attributed to the synthetic

Figure 4: Comparison of our results with values from the literature. The errorbars of this work are plotted in gray. Different determination methods are marked with different symbols. The ellipse in the top panel marks the outlier star GJ 87 (J02123+035). Legend: fit (synthetic spectrum fit): Passegger et al. (2019), Gaidos & Mann (2014) (T_{eff} VIS), Mann et al. (2015) (T_{eff}); spec (pEWs, spectral indices, spectroscopic relations): Rojas-Ayala et al. (2012); Maldonado et al. (2015), Gaidos & Mann (2014) (T_{eff} NIR, $\log g$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$), Mann et al. (2015) ($\log g$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$), Terrien et al. (2015); ML: Antoniadis-Karnavas et al. (2020); phot (photometric): Dittmann et al. (2016); Houdebine et al. (2019); interfer (interferometry): Maldonado et al. (2015). Figure taken from Passegger et al. (2020), Fig. 7.

Figure 5: Preliminary results of DTL for T_{eff} . Literature values are color-coded, including our previous results from DL (black).

gap. To reduce uncertainties from the synthetic gap, we recently introduced Deep Transfer Learning in our algorithm. For T_{eff} , we therefore transfer knowledge gained from interferometrically determined T_{eff} for a few stars to the rest of the CARMENES sample. We can see that T_{eff} predicted from DTL show slightly smaller mean differences to literature values than DL. We will also apply DTL to $\log g$ and metallicity in a next step.

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References

- Abadi, e. a., M. 2015, *TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Systems*. <https://github.com/tensorflow/tensorflow>. Accessed: 2020-02-07.
- Abraham, S., Aniyán, A. K., Kembhavi, A. K., Philip, N. S., & Vaghmare, K. 2018, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 477, 894. ISSN 0035-8711.
- Anthony, M. & Bartlett, P. L. 2009, *Neural network learning: Theoretical foundations* (cambridge university press).
- Antoniadis-Karnavas, A., Sousa, S. G., Delgado-Mena, E., Santos, N. C., Teixeira, G. D. C., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 636, A9.
- Birky, J., Hogg, D. W., Mann, A. W., & Burgasser, A. 2020, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 892, 31.
- Boyajian, T. S., von Braun, K., van Belle, G., McAlister, H. A., ten Brummelaar, T. A., et al. 2012, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 757, 112.
- Boyajian, T. S., McAlister, H. A., Baines, E. K., Gies, D. R., Henry, T., et al. 2008, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 683, 424.
- von Braun, K., Boyajian, T. S., van Belle, G. T., Kane, S. R., Jones, J., et al. 2014, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 438, 2413.
- Bressan, A., Marigo, P., Girardi, L., Salasnich, B., Dal Cero, C., et al. 2012, *MNRAS*, 427, 127.
- Chen, Y., Bressan, A., Girardi, L., Marigo, P., Kong, X., et al. 2015, *MNRAS*, 452, 1068.
- Chen, Y., Girardi, L., Bressan, A., Marigo, P., Barbieri, M., et al. 2014, *MNRAS*, 444, 2525.
- Chollet, F. 2015, *KERAS*. <https://github.com/keras-team/keras>. Accessed: 2020-02-07.
- Czesla, S., Schröter, S., Schneider, C. P., Huber, K. F., Pfeifer, F., et al. 2019, *PyA: Python astronomy-related packages*.
- Dieleman, S., Willett, K. W., & Dambre, J. 2015, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 450, 1441. ISSN 0035-8711.
- Dittmann, J. A., Irwin, J. M., Charbonneau, D., & Newton, E. R. 2016, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 818, 153.
- Fabbro, S., Venn, K. A., O’Brian, T., Bialek, S., Kielty, C. L., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 475, 2978.
- Figueira, P., Adibekyan, V. Z., Oshagh, M., Neal, J. J., Rojas-Ayala, B., et al. 2016, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 586, A101.
- Gaidos, E. & Mann, A. W. 2014, *ApJ*, 791, 54.
- Gong, B. & Ordieres-Meré, J. 2016, *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 84, 290.
- Hauschildt, P. H. 1992, , 47, 433.
- Hauschildt, P. H. 1993, , 50, 301.
- Hauschildt, P. H. & Baron, E. 1999, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 109, 41.
- Hon, M., Stello, D., & Yu, J. 2017, *MNRAS*, 469, 4578.
- Houdebine, É. R., Mullan, D. J., Doyle, J. G., de La Vieuville, G., Butler, C. J., et al. 2019, *The Astronomical Journal*, 158, 56.
- Husser, T.-O., Wende-von Berg, S., Dreizler, S., Homeier, D., Reiners, A., et al. 2013, *A&A*, 553, A6.
- LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., & Hinton, G. 2015, *nature*, 521, 436.
- Mahabal, A., Sheth, K., Gieseke, F., Pai, A., Djorgovski, S. G., et al. 2017, *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1709.06257.
- Maldonado, J., Affer, L., Micela, G., Scandariato, G., Damasso, M., et al. 2015, *A&A*, 577, A132.
- Mann, A. W., Feiden, G. A., Gaidos, E., Boyajian, T., & von Braun, K. 2015, *ApJ*, 804, 64.
- McInnes, L., Healy, J., Saul, N., & Grossberger, L. 2018, *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 3, 861.
- Montes, D., González-Peinado, R., Tabernero, H. M., Caballero, J. A., Marfil, E., et al. 2018, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 479, 1332.
- Nagel, E., Czesla, S., Kaminski, A., Zechmeister, M., Tal-Or, L., et al. 2021, submitted, *A&A*.
- Ness, M., Hogg, D. W., Rix, H. W., Ho, A. Y. Q., & Zasowski, G. 2015, *ApJ*, 808, 16.
- Parzen, E. 1962, *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 33, 1065.
- Passegger, V. M., Bello-García, A., Ordieres-Meré, J., Caballero, J. A., Schweitzer, A., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 642, A22.
- Passegger, V. M., Reiners, A., Jeffers, S. V., Wende-von Berg, S., Schöfer, P., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 615, A6.
- Passegger, V. M., Schweitzer, A., Shulyak, D., Nagel, E., Hauschildt, P. H., et al. 2019, *A&A*, 627, A161.
- Quirrenbach, A., Amado, P. J., Ribas, I., Reiners, A., Caballero, J. A., et al. 2018, In *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, vol. 10702, p. 107020W.
- Reiners, A., Zechmeister, M., Caballero, J. A., Ribas, I., Morales, J. C., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 612, A49.
- Rojas-Ayala, B., Covey, K. R., Muirhead, P. S., & Lloyd, J. P. 2012, *ApJ*, 748, 93.
- Rosenblatt, M. 1956, *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 27, 832.
- Sarro, L. M., Ordieres-Meré, J., Bello-García, A., González-Marcos, A., & Solano, E. 2018, *MNRAS*, 476, 1120.
- Schmidhuber, J. 2015, *Neural networks*, 61, 85.
- Tang, J., Bressan, A., Rosenfield, P., Slemmer, A., Marigo, P., et al. 2014, *MNRAS*, 445, 4287.
- Terrien, R. C., Mahadevan, S., Bender, C. F., Deshpande, R., & Robertson, P. 2015, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 802, L10.
- Vilalta, R. 2018, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1085, 052014.
- Whitten, D. D., Placco, V. M., Beers, T. C., Chies-Santos, A. L., Bonatto, C., et al. 2019, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 622, A182.
- Wu, C., Wong, O. I., Rudnick, L., Shabala, S. S., Alger, M. J., et al. 2018, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 482, 1211. ISSN 0035-8711.
- Zechmeister, M., Reiners, A., Amado, P. J., Azzaro, M., Bauer, F. F., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 609, A12.
- Zhang, G., Patuwo, B. E., & Hu, M. Y. 1998, *International journal of forecasting*, 14, 35.
- Zheng, X., Wang, M., & Ordieres-Meré, J. 2018, *Sensors*, 18, 2146.